

MODELING A PROGNOSTIC PROGRAM FOR PATIENTS WITH HORMONE-RESISTANT PROSTATE CANCER

Iskandarov.J.M. ¹

Boyko.E.B. ²

Hasanov.Sh.T. ²

Yusupov.Sh.H. ³

Bukhara branch of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of oncology and radiology ¹

Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of oncology and radiology ²

Tashkent city branch of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of oncology and radiology ³

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Hormonal tumor resistance in some patients with prostate cancer is determined immediately from the start of treatment, while in others it develops after several months of successful treatment with hormonal therapy. Despite this, there are still no characteristic signs or reliable criteria for determining primary and secondary forms of hormonal resistance, which makes it difficult to choose adequate therapy for each patient with prostate cancer.

Objective: to study the likelihood of developing hormone resistance in patients with prostate cancer using prognostic criteria based on computer modulation

Materials and methods: we conducted a retrospective analysis of 112 patients with HRPC to determine the dependence on the likelihood of developing hormone resistance in patients with prostate cancer.

In the course of scientific research, we have made and rejected many combinations of prognostic factors. The most responsive to our requirements today, based on our capabilities, was a prognostic program that included a combination of the following signs: PSA, Gleason sum, degree of differentiation, expression of androgen receptors (AR), CD34.

Based on these indicators, we developed and tested the following prognostic program using computer modulation:

1. Favorable prognosis: Gleason score < 6, PSA < 10 ng/ml, moderate degree of tumor differentiation, high AR expression, low adrenal testosterone, absence or low CD34 expression
2. Intermediate prognosis: PSA 10-20 ng/ml or Gleason score 7, high degree of tumor differentiation, moderate AR expression, moderate adrenal testosterone, moderate CD34 expression;

3. Poor prognosis: Gleason score > 7 or PSA > 20 ng/ml, low tumor differentiation, low AR expression, high adrenal testosterone, high CD34

expression

Results: At the same time, the sum of points equal to 12.1 to 17 correlates with an unfavorable prognosis, from 12 to 7.1 intermediate and the sum of points from 7.0 to 5.1 correlates with a favorable outcome of the disease. In the course of scientific research, we have made and rejected many combinations of prognostic factors. The most responsive to our requirements today, based on our capabilities, turned out to be a prognostic program that includes a combination of the following signs: PSA less than 10 mg/ml factor load (FL) 3.1 ($p < 0.05$), Gleason sum less than 7 FN 2, 4 ($p < 0.05$), degree of differentiation G3 FN 2.2 ($p < 0.05$) and G4 2.7 ($p < 0.05$), expression of androgen receptors (AR), CD 34 high expression 4.2 ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: in this way, this model, using the method of simple summation of individual factors, determined how favorable (or unfavorable) the symptom being tested is. Despite this, the prognostic program we developed can predict the outcome of the disease with an accuracy of up to $70 \pm 2.7\%$.

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